

VIRTUAL TESTING OF FOLDCORES MADE OF POLYETHYLENE TEREPHTHALATE

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ABSTRACT

Sandwich structures with foldcores made by folding thin material into a three-dimensional configuration using the principle of origami are regarded as a promising alternative to conventional honeycomb sandwich structures as lightweight structural materials. While aluminium and CFRP foldcores have been intensively studied in recent years, there lacks published research work on foldcores made of thermoplastic materials that might have advantages in low-cost fabrication and specific impact energy absorption performance. In this paper, a validated virtual testing protocol based on finite element simulations is established for the investigation of the mechanical behaviors of foldcores made of polyethylene terephthalate (PET), a typical thermoplastic material. Several important modelling issues such as the cell wall material modelling, the influences of element size and loading rate are investigated. PET foldcore prototypes based on a given standard Miura pattern manufactured by means of vacuum moulding technique are physically tested on a universal testing machine. A comparison between the numerical and experimental results shows a good correlation with respect to cell wall deformation mechanisms and stress-strain data, indicating that these numerical models in virtual tests allow for accurate mechanical characterizations of PET foldcores and for a detailed investigation of cell wall deformation patterns that helps one to get a better understanding of the structural behavior. Finally, a parameter study of various types of PET foldcores generated by the vertex method was performed. Initial results show that PET foldcores provide a relatively large design space.

1 INTRODUCTION

Composite sandwich structures, typically consisting of two thin and stiff faces separated by a thick lightweight cellular core, have been used in many industrial sectors like automotive and aerospace industries. In recent years, sandwich structures with foldcores fabricated by folding thin material into a three-dimensional configuration using the principle of origami emerged as a promising alternative to conventional sandwich structures. This origami-like foldcore family is open to various base materials and unit cell geometries. As a result, a number of numerical studies of foldcore sandwich structures, such as virtual in- and out-of-plane quasi-static compression and shear tests [1-6], low- and high-velocity impact simulations [7-9], residual bending strength simulations after impact [10] and macro- and multi-scale modelling [3,8], are available in the literature. However, current research work mainly focuses on aluminium, aramid and CFRP foldcores. So far, the authors are not aware of any literature on computational or experimental study of foldcores made of thermoplastic materials although they have potential advantages in low-cost fabrication and specific impact energy absorption performance.

In this paper, we report a preliminary study on the mechanical behaviors of foldcores made of polyethylene terephthalate (PET), a typical thermoplastic material using a validated virtual testing

protocol based on the finite element (FE) simulation. Several important modelling issues such as the cell wall material modelling, the influences of element size and loading rate are investigated. PET foldcore prototypes based on a given standard Miura pattern manufactured by means of vacuum moulding technique are physically tested on a universal testing machine. A comparison between the numerical and experimental results shows a good correlation with respect to cell wall deformation mechanisms and stress-strain data, indicating that these numerical models in virtual tests allow for accurate mechanical characterizations of PET foldcores and for a detailed investigation of cell wall deformation patterns that helps one to get a better understanding of the structural behavior. Finally, a parameter study of three different types of PET foldcore generated by the vertex method was performed. Initial results show that PET foldcores provide a relatively large design space.

2 MODELLING OF PET FOLDCORES

2.1 Base material model

The dimensions of the test specimen used for the material test are shown in Fig. 1. The specimens are cut out of a 0.26 mm thick PET sheet. The uniaxial tensile tests were performed on a Zwick/Roell Z100 materials testing machine. The stress-strain curves of the tensile tests are shown in Fig. 2. According to the test results, an elastic-plastic isotropic material model was employed to model the base material. Since only quasi-static loading processes were considered in this paper, the effect of strain rate was not considered. The detailed material properties are summarized in Tables 1 and 2.

Figure 1: The test specimen.

Figure 2: Tensile stress-strain results of specimens.

Base material	ρ_m [kg/m ³]	E [MPa]	σ_y [MPa]	ν
PET sheet	1350	2665	28.58	0.39

Table 1: The elastic properties of the base material.

ε^{pl}	σ [MPa]	ε^{pl}	σ [MPa]
0.001	43.82	0.008	67.93
0.002	51.68	0.009	68.85
0.003	56.79	0.010	69.46
0.004	60.64	0.011	69.86
0.005	63.31	0.012	70.17
0.006	65.26	0.013	70.34
0.007	66.88	0.014	70.45

Table 2: The plastic properties of the base material.

2.2 Geometrical modelling

In this paper, the geometrical model of the foldcore is generated using the vertex method [6]. In this method, m input points in the x - z plane \mathbf{V}_i^x , $i = 1, 2, \dots, m$ and $n + 2$ input points in the y - z plane \mathbf{V}_j^y , $j = 0, 1, \dots, n + 1$ are first specified in a Cartesian coordinate system and then $m \times n$ vertices $\mathbf{V}_{i,j}$ of the target foldcore geometric model are obtained using the following equation

$$\mathbf{V}_{i,j} = \begin{bmatrix} x_{i,j} \\ y_{i,j} \\ z_{i,j} \end{bmatrix} = \mathbf{V}_j^y + [\mathbf{A}_j] \mathbf{V}_i^x, i = 1, 2, \dots, m; j = 1, 2, \dots, n, \quad (1)$$

where $[\mathbf{A}_j]$ is a 3×3 matrix given by

$$[\mathbf{A}_j] = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & (-1)^j \frac{\cos \theta_{j-1} + \cos \theta_j}{\sin(\theta_{j-1} - \theta_j)} \\ 0 & 0 & (-1)^j \frac{\sin \theta_{j-1} + \sin \theta_j}{\sin(\theta_{j-1} - \theta_j)} \end{bmatrix} \quad (2)$$

where the angular variable θ_j is determined by

$$\sin \theta_j = \frac{\mathbf{i}_z \cdot (\mathbf{V}_{j+1}^y - \mathbf{V}_j^y)}{\|\mathbf{V}_{j+1}^y - \mathbf{V}_j^y\|} \quad (3)$$

$$\cos \theta_j = \frac{\mathbf{i}_y \cdot (\mathbf{V}_{j+1}^y - \mathbf{V}_j^y)}{\|\mathbf{V}_{j+1}^y - \mathbf{V}_j^y\|} \quad (4)$$

where $\mathbf{i}_y = [0 \ 1 \ 0]^T$ and $\mathbf{i}_z = [0 \ 0 \ 1]^T$ are the unit vectors of the y and z axis, respectively, and $\|\mathbf{u}\|$ denotes the norm of a vector \mathbf{u} .

Consider the input point sets in the x - z and y - z planes shown in Fig. 3, where parameters α , h_x , β and h_y are taken as 40.32° , 8.49 mm, 45° and 10 mm, respectively. The resulting structure, denoted by UM1, is a unit cell of the standard Miura pattern whose x -width, y -width and height are 20 mm, 20 mm and 10 mm, respectively, as shown in Fig. 4. The base area of the unit cell, defined as the area of the projected shadow in the x - y plane, is equal to 400 mm².

2.3 Influence of modelling parameters

The virtual tests were implemented in the FE solver ABAQUS/Explicit (SIMULIA Inc., USA) due to its good capability to cope with large nonlinear deformation, post-buckling behaviour and

Figure 3: The input point sets in the x - z and y - z planes to generate model UM1.

Figure 4: Model UM1 – a unit cell of the standard Miura pattern.

complicated contact conditions. Due to the nature of explicit FE analysis for solving dynamic problems, the loading-rate has to be carefully chosen so that quasi-static procedures are completed within realistic computational time. S4R, i.e. the four-node quadrilateral shell element with reduced integration and hourglass control in ABAQUS, is employed to mesh the foldcore. With this particular element type, the mesh density has a strong influence on the accuracy of the simulation results. Because the stable time increment of explicit FE analysis is proportional to the element length, increasing element size significantly reduces the computational time. However, a coarser mesh is not able to accurately represent the post-buckling behavior of the facets, leading to higher post-buckling stress levels. Therefore, both loading rate and mesh density convergence tests are necessary steps to guarantee meaningful virtual test results.

For model UM1, the convergence tests were conducted by free compression of the model in the z -direction between two rigid plates that are parallel to the x - y plane. In the loading rate and mesh density convergence tests, velocities of 250 mm/s to 2000 mm/s and element sizes of 0.125 mm to 2 mm were compared, respectively. The results are shown in Figs. 5 and 6. According to the results, 500 mm/s and 0.25 mm are taken as the converged values for loading rate and element size, respectively.

3 EXPERIMENTAL TESTING OF PET FOLDCORES

3.1 Manufacturing of PET foldcores

The vacuum moulding method we used to manufacture PET foldcores is schematically illustrated in Fig. 7. In this method, an aluminium mould is machined according to the geometrical model of the

Figure 5: Loading rate convergence test result of UM1.

Figure 6: Mesh density convergence test result of UM1.

foldcore. Through holes of small diameter are drilled at locations on the mould corresponding to the bottom vertices of the foldcore. The PET sheet is firmly placed on the top of the mould and is heated above the glass transition temperature T_g of the material by hot air. Once the PET sheet turns to soft, the air between the PET sheet and the mould is sucked out through the air holes by a vacuum pump.

Figure 7: Diagram of the vacuum moulding method to manufacture PET foldcores.

Figure 8: A manufactured PET foldcore test sample consisting of 3×3 UM1s.

At the same time, the PET sheet is pressed onto the corrugated surface of the mould by air pressure. Once the PET sheet is cooled to room temperature, it stays in the pressed state. Figure 8 shows a manufactured foldcore test sample consisting of 3×3 UM1s.

3.2 Comparison of experimental and virtual test results

The compression tests of four foldcore test samples shown in Fig. 8 were performed on a MTS universal testing machine. In each test, the foldcore was placed between flat platens of the testing machine and compressed by 5 mm in the thickness direction, resulting in a maximum loaded effective strain of 50%. Meanwhile, a virtual test was carried out to simulate the experiment. Because the creases of the test samples are rounded instead of sharp edges, this imperfection was introduced into the numerical model of the foldcore by replacing each crease with a round corner of 0.1 mm radius.

Figure 9 shows the effective compressive stress-strain curves of the experimental and virtual tests and the deformed shapes of the foldcore during the experimental and the virtual test are shown in Fig. 10. A good agreement between the experimental and virtual test results was observed.

4 PARAMETER STUDY OF PET FOLDCORES

In this section, a parameter study of the mechanical properties of PET foldcores with different input point sets in the x - z plane is performed. Three foldcore models M1-M3 that consist of 3×3 unit cell models UM1-UM3, respectively were considered, where unit cell models UM2 and UM3 are obtained by replacing the input point set in the x - z plane in Fig. 3 with those shown in Fig. 11. The density ρ_c of the foldcore can be obtained by

$$\rho_c = \frac{t_m S_m}{V_u} \rho_m \quad (5)$$

Figure 9: Comparison of the stress-strain curves in experiment and virtual test.

Figure 10: Comparison of deformations of the foldcore in experiment (a) and virtual test (b).

where t_m , S_m and ρ_m are respectively the thickness, total area and density of the base material from which a unit cell of the core is folded and V_u is the spatial volume of the unit cell, defined by

$$V_u = S_u H_c \quad (6)$$

where H_c and S_u is the height and the projected area in the x - y plane of the foldcore. To facilitate the comparison of the weight-specific mechanical properties of the foldcores, a unified foldcore density is imposed. According to Eqns. (5) and (6), there is

$$\left. \frac{t_m S_m}{S_u H_c} \right|_{UM1} = \left. \frac{t_m S_m}{S_u H_c} \right|_{UM2} = \left. \frac{t_m S_m}{S_u H_c} \right|_{UM3} \quad (7)$$

The geometric parameters of unit cell models UM1-UM3 are summarized in Table 3.

Foldcore models M1-M3 used in the virtual tests are shown in Fig. 12. They were meshed with S4R elements with an average element size of 0.25 mm according to the mesh convergence study, resulting in 127224, 147744 and 143640 elements for models M1, M2 and M3, respectively. Two types of virtual tests, i.e. free compression and bonded compression, were considered. The free compression test is the same as that described in Section 2.3. In the bonded compression test, the foldcores were bonded to the rigid plates using the tie constraint. In both virtual tests, the general contact algorithm was employed to model the self-contact of the folded core and the surface-to-surface contact between the core and each rigid plate. The foldcores were compressed by 5 mm at a loading-rate of 500 mm/s according to the loading-rate convergence study, resulting in a maximum loaded compressive strain of 50%.

The compressive stress-strain curves of models M1-M3 in the free compression tests were shown in Fig. 13. It is noted that models M1 and M3 have the lowest and highest compressive stiffness, respectively. While model M3 have the highest compressive strength, the difference of the compressive strength among the models is not significant. The compressive stress-strain curves in the bonded compression tests were shown in Fig. 14. The curves are characterized by well-defined peaks due to buckling followed by folding of the facets. Different from the results in the free compression

Figure 11: The input point sets in the x - z plane to generate model UM2 and UM3.

Figure 12: The foldcore models M1-M3.

Model	H_c [mm]	S_u [mm ²]	S_m [mm ²]	t_m [mm]
UM1	10	400	741.89	0.26
UM2	10	400	839.98	0.2296
UM3	10	400	822.66	0.2345

Table 3: The geometric parameters of unit cell models UM1-UM3.

Figure 13: The stress-strain curves of models M1-M3 in the free compression tests.

Figure 14: The stress-strain curves of models M1-M3 in the bonded compression tests.

tests, the stiffnesses of the models are close to each other while the compressive strength increases from M1 to M3. In both loading types, model M3 that features curved creases exhibits the highest strength and / or stiffness.

5 CONCLUSIONS

A virtual test method based on the dynamic finite element simulation was developed to simulate the mechanical properties of PET foldcores, in which the geometrical models of the foldcores were obtained using the vertex method. To validate the numerical model, the vacuum moulding method was used to manufacture PET foldcore test samples. A comparison between the virtual and experimental tests of the PET foldcores under free compression shows a good correlation with respect to cell wall deformation mechanisms and stress-strain data. Therefore, the virtual test method can be used as an efficient alternative to experimental tests for the characterization of the mechanical properties of PET foldcores.

Using the validated virtual test method, we investigated the mechanical properties of three types of foldcores subject to free and bonded compressive loads. It is shown that the compressive stiffness and strength of these foldcores vary notably with the change in the input point set in the x - z plane, indicating a potential large design space achievable by PET foldcores.

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